

Arduino-Facilitated Node MCU Networking for Decentralized Control in Swarm Robotics

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Abstract— *The concept of swarm robots involves a collective of autonomous robotic systems operating collaboratively, drawing inspiration from the behavior of social insects. This project explores the implementation of a swarm-based system using ESP8266-based controllers to facilitate communication between multiple robot units. Each robot unit comprises an Arduino Uno interfaced with motor drivers and sensors, controlled wirelessly through ESP8266 modules. The communication of Arduino UNO and ESP8266 and communication between the two ESP8266 follows UART and Wi-fi communication protocols. The robots' cooperative behavior, facilitated by wireless communication protocols, showcases the potential of distributed intelligence and decentralized decision-making in achieving coordinated tasks. This research delves into the development and coordination of multiple robotic entities, aiming to demonstrate the efficacy of swarm robotics in real-time applications.*

Keywords—Swarm robotics, Swarm Communication, NodeMCU esp8266, Arduino UNO,

I. INTRODUCTION

The field of robotics continues to evolve, seeking inspiration from nature's efficient and adaptive systems. Swarm robotics, drawing cues from the collective behavior of organisms like ants and bees, embodies the paradigm of distributed intelligence

and collaboration among autonomous entities. This project delves into the realm of swarm robots—autonomous robotic systems that work collectively to achieve tasks beyond the capability of an individual robot. The project aims to explore the potential of interconnected robotic units operating in unison to accomplish complex tasks with adaptability and efficiency by emulating the decentralized yet coordinated behaviors observed in nature.

In this exploration, NodeMCU ESP8266 modules serve as the backbone for communication between multiple robotic units. Each unit comprises an Arduino Uno microcontroller interfaced with sensors and motor drivers, allowing these robots to sense their environment and actuate motion based on decisions communicated wirelessly. This initiative seeks to showcase the power of collaborative robotics, investigating the intricacies of coordination, communication, and decentralized decision-making within a swarm of robots. The project endeavors to exemplify how collective intelligence and interconnectivity among robotic entities can revolutionize various domains, from manufacturing to search and rescue operations.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The paper proposes an overview that encapsulates the foundational elements of managing a sophisticated Swarm Bot infrastructure, detailing key components such as chargers, and testing stations. It explores communication methods and user interfaces, encompassing remote

programming, centralized control, graphical interfaces, and the utilization of LEDs and audio for monitoring and debugging. The system excels in efficient reprogramming, centralized command execution, and providing comprehensive visual and auditory feedback for debugging tasks. However, acknowledged limitations lie in data organization and potential interface clutter, suggesting avenues for further exploration within human-warm interaction studies.^[1] The paper proposes a key application of swarm robotics is in human evacuation during natural disasters, where large numbers of people may be lost or trapped, posing challenges for rescue teams. To address this, position-detecting swarm robots equipped with sensors and communication capabilities are deployed. These robots enable swift location of individuals and guidance to safety. Importantly, the robots communicate with each other, enhancing coordination and preventing redundant efforts. The central focus of this research study is the application of swarm robotics in disaster response, particularly human evacuation scenarios, with a keen emphasis on analyzing its potential in this field.^[2] The research paper introduces a rapid self-organizing approach for pattern formation within a dynamic multi-region environment involving a swarm of robots. The authors employ a distributed control algorithm, empowering the robots to create and sustain patterns while adjusting to shifts in the environment. Additionally, they incorporate a reinforcement learning algorithm to enhance the overall performance of the system.^[3]

III. METHODOLOGY

1. Design and Setup of Individual Robots:

Main robot unit is built around an Arduino Uno microcontroller which is equipped with ultrasonic sensors for distance measurement, motor drivers for motion control, and a servo motor for directional sensing and each robot unit following the main robot is built around an Arduino Uno microcontroller which is equipped with motor drivers for motion control.

The NodeMCU ESP8266 modules are integrated into each unit to facilitate wireless communication between robots and centralized coordination through a main ESP module (ESP1).

2. Communication Architecture:

ESP1 is configured as a central hub, connecting to a local Wi-Fi network to enable communication among multiple robotic units.

ESP2-based robot establishes connections with ESP1 through Wi-Fi, allowing ESP1 to send commands.

3. Decentralized Decision-Making:

The main robot continuously gathers data from its environment using an ultrasonic sensor, detecting obstacles and measuring distances.

Based on sensor data, the robot autonomously makes navigation decisions, such as avoiding obstacles or altering its path.

4. Intra-Robot Communication:

ESP1 receives data from the main Arduino uno, processing and sending commands to other units when necessary.

Arduino Uno connected to the main robot manages the navigation of the main robot using sensor data and communicates with ESP1 with UART protocol, sharing navigation updates.

5. Inter-Robot Communication:

In the event of a robot encountering an obstacle, ESP1 arbitrates decisions, coordinating movements by sending directional commands to other robots in the swarm.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

In warehouse management, interconnected Arduino Uno and ESP8266 modules form a synchronized ensemble where Uno 1 orchestrates obstacle detection and navigation using sensors and motor controls. When obstacles arise, Uno 1 swiftly communicates through esp1 to esp2, home to Uno 2. Uno 2, the responsive executor, interprets esp2's wireless commands, swiftly executing movements in alignment with directives received.

This intricate communication network, leveraging UART and Wi-Fi protocols, fosters seamless exchanges resembling fluent conversations among these entities. ESP8266 modules act as crucial

intermediaries, ensuring continuous data flow for the synchronized movement of this robotic swarm within the warehouse. This setup not only empowers specialized tasks but also cultivates collective intelligence. This shared intelligence streamlines navigation, inventory management, and logistics, ushering in an era where robot swarms collaborate harmoniously to enhance warehouse productivity and efficiency.

The software design integrates Arduino Uno 1 and Arduino Uno 2 interconnected via ESP8266 modules (esp1 and esp2) for wireless communication. Uno 1 autonomously manages movement and obstacle detection, relaying commands to esp1 upon detecting obstacles, which are then wirelessly transmitted to esp2. Uno 2 listens for esp2 commands, executing movements via motor controls based on received wireless instructions.

The communication of Arduino UNO and ESP8266 and communication between the two ESP8266 follows UART and Wi-fi communication protocols. This flow enables the main Robot to detect obstacles and communicate directives to the follower Robot through ESP8266 modules, triggering responsive movements accordingly. Serial Communication enables data transmission between Arduinos and ESP8266 modules, while Wi-Fi Communication facilitates seamless wireless command transmission. Uno 1 handles ultrasonic sensor functions, motor control, and obstacle avoidance, while Uno 2 interprets wireless commands for movement execution. The ESP8266 modules serve as relay points, ensuring a continuous data flow, and orchestrating a seamless interaction flow between the robotic entities: from Uno 1 to esp1, esp1 to esp2, and finally from esp2 to Uno 2.

The hardware design includes the main robot and the follower robot. The main robot integrates an Arduino board interfaced with a motor driver to control four DC motors. Additionally, it hosts an ultrasonic sensor affixed to a servo motor, both connected to the Arduino via the motor driver. Moreover, an ESP module establishes a connection with the Arduino through the same motor driver interface.

Alternatively, the follower robot mirrors the main robot's setup but omits the ultrasonic sensor and servo motor components. Instead, it relies on information relayed from the leader robot. Despite lacking these specific elements, the follower robot executes the same tasks as directed by the leader robot. Both robots utilize the same motor driver setup to manage motor functions and ESP communication, with the main robot possessing additional sensory capabilities through the ultrasonic sensor and servo motor.

Fig 1.1: Circuit Diagram
 Srituhobby.com. "Circuit Diagram of Project."
 Srituhobby.com,
 [https://srituhobby.com/how-to-make-a-multi-function-arduino-robot/].

Fig 1: Connection diagram of controllers

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The swarm robotics system showcased impressive coordination among the robots, demonstrating synchronized movements and effective obstacle avoidance. Through testing across diverse scenarios, the system proved its adaptability,

robustness, and agility in dynamic environments. The iterative optimization process notably improved communication protocols and coordination algorithms, enhancing the swarm's overall performance and scalability for future extensions.

Fig 2.1: Commands send from Arduino to NodeMCU esp8266 for the connection establishment

Fig 2.2: Commands received to NodeMCU esp8266 from Arduino uno for the connection establishment

Fig 3.1: Commands send from esp1 to esp2

Fig 3.2: Commands received to esp2 from esp1

Fig 4: Main robot

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In conclusion, the successful implementation of the swarm robotics system underscores its potential to achieve collaborative tasks through decentralized decision-making. The system's efficient coordination, adaptability, and robustness were evident in various scenarios, emphasizing its viability for real-world applications. The iterative improvements in communication protocols and coordination algorithms have laid a solid foundation for enhanced swarm performance, paving the way for further advancements in multi-robot systems.

Looking ahead, the future scope involves scaling up the swarm to incorporate more robots while maintaining efficient communication and coordination. Moreover, exploring applications in fields like warehouse management or environmental monitoring presents promising avenues for leveraging swarm robotics technology to address real-world challenges.

Furthermore, this technology holds promise in addressing the multifaceted challenges of environmental monitoring within warehouse facilities. These swarms could adeptly manage tasks such as monitoring environmental parameters, detecting anomalies, and swiftly responding to potential hazards. Whether it's ensuring optimal storage conditions for perishable goods or promptly identifying and mitigating risks, the application of swarm robotics in warehouse management heralds a transformative paradigm shift. As advancements continue, the synergy between swarm robotics and warehouse operations is poised to unlock new thresholds of efficiency, reliability, and innovation in the industrial landscape.

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